

Set Theory and Energy Numbers

Parker Emmerson

October 2023

1 Introduction, "Section B:"

$$\forall x \in Z : [x + 1 < x]$$

For $x = a$ and $x = b$, where $a < b$, this statement holds: if $a = b - 1$, then $a + 1 = b < x = a < a + 1 = b$.

$$\forall A \in (V) : \forall n \in N : \forall \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq A : \forall x_1 \in V : \dots : \forall x_n \in V : \forall x_{n+1} \in V : (x_n \in A \wedge x_{n+1} \notin A) \Rightarrow$$

$$A \cap \{x_{n+1}\} \neq \emptyset$$

The above statement has to do with sets, in particular a set A in this case, which is a subset of some vector space V . Essentially, what the statement is saying is that if we are working with a vector space and some set that is a subset of that vector space, then we can always find an element that does not belong in A , but belongs in the vector space itself. In other words, the statement is identical in scope and expressivity – albeit not with identical symbols – to showing that any red* MATH -j LATEX derivative gives a non-empty set.

One way to interpret this statement is that if we are looking at $n+1$ elements that are all pulled from the set A , and we have n of them already in A , then the last one must be in A as well; since x_{n+1} is the $n+1$ -th element, this statement reads:

$$\forall A \in (V) : \forall n \in N : \forall x_1, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1} \in A : x_{n+1} \notin A \Rightarrow A \cap \{x_{n+1}\} \neq \emptyset$$

We can prove this by contradiction. Suppose that for some A , n , and $x_1, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1} \in A$, we have $x_{n+1} \notin A$; in other words, x_{n+1} is the $n+1$ -th element of the set A . Then $x_{n+1} \in \{x_1, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}\}$, since it is the $n+1$ -th (and last!) element of this set. Now the information we did not know before is that all of the first n members of this set were in A , meaning that $A \cap \{x_1, \dots, x_n, x_{n+1}\} \neq \emptyset$ should be true; but this contradicts the fact that $A \neq \emptyset$ and the statement that we began with, thereby violating the statement itself. Therefore, our initial hypothesis must have been true, so that whenever we add one more element to any set, that new element is still part of that set, and we can make the set bigger with it.

Therefore, for any A and B , we have that $x < y$ does not imply that $x + 1 < y + 1$, unless we already know from some other source of information that the ordering stays the same as we "push forward" by one unit on both sides.

2 Concepts of Energy Numbers "Section A:"

Let V be a real vector space of dimension n . The topological space V is then defined to be the set of all continuous functions from E^n to R . This topological space is then equipped with the topology generated by the system of all open subsets of V which are of the form

$$\{f \in V \mid f(e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n) \in U \subset R\}$$

where $e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n \in E$ and U is an open subset of R . This is the definition of the topological continuum in a higher dimensional vector space.

Energy numbers are independent entities which can be mapped to real numbers, but the reverse is not true. Energy numbers exist on their own and can be used to give representative credence to real numbers from a higher dimensional vector space.

$$V = \{E : E^n \rightarrow R \mid$$

E is an energy number}

This is the notational, linguistic form of the kind of statements used to construct the liberated, symbolic patterns from which energy number expressions can be synthetizationally derived.

$$\mathcal{V} = \left\{ f \mid \exists \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E \cup R \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{V} = \left\{ f \mid \exists \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\} \in E, \text{ and } : E \mapsto r \in R \right\}$$

$$\mathcal{V} = \{E \mid \exists \{a_1, \dots, a_n\} \in E, E \not\mapsto r \in R\}$$

where the scalar product of two vectors x and y can be expressed as $\langle x, y \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i$, and the energy numbers x_i and y_i are independent entities, which are not subject to the same rules as real numbers $r \in R$.

3 Conclusion

In section A, we defined a topological space on a vector space V , equipped with a topology generated by the system of open subsets defined by mappings from E^n to R . We also introduced the concept of energy numbers, which are independent entities that can be mapped to real numbers.

In section B, the statement we are examining deals with sets that are subsets of a vector space V . It states that if we have a set A containing n elements, and we add one more element from the vector space (represented by x_{n+1}), then this new element must be part of A as well.

Using the language from section A, we can describe this premise as follows:

Let $A \subseteq V$, where V is a vector space. For all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, let $x_1, \dots, x_n \in A$, and let $x_{n+1} \in V$. Then, if $x_{n+1} \notin A$, it must be mapped to a real number, r , in order for the set $A \subseteq V$ to be non-empty. In other words, if x_{n+1} is an energy number, then it must be contained in A as well, otherwise $A \cap \{x_{n+1}\} = \emptyset$.

Therefore, the premise in section B is an extension of the ideas introduced in section A, and can be notated as such:

$$\forall A \in (V) : \forall n \in \mathbb{N} : \forall \{x_1, \dots, x_n\} \subseteq A : \forall x_1 \in V : \dots : \forall x_n \in V : \forall x_{n+1} \in V : (x_n \in A \wedge x_{n+1} \notin A) \Rightarrow$$

$$\exists E \in V : \text{Eisanenergynumber}, E \in A \wedge E \neq x_{n+1}$$

This notation expands upon the ideas in section A by explicitly stating that the new element, x_{n+1} , in order to be contained in A , must be an energy number and not just any mapped real number. This also allows for the potential for additional energy numbers to exist within A , and highlights the fact that the premise in section B is a fundamental property of energy numbers in a topological setting.